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From Social Constrict to Personal Freedom: A Comparative Study of the Portrayal of Marriage in Selected Movies Illuminating the Transformations in Marital Relationships from the Victorian Era to the Present Day

Sreelakshmi Remesh

Department of English,
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham,
Amritapuri, India.

Ardra C Pillai

Department of English,
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham,
Amritapuri, India.

Shilpa M Chandran

Department of English,
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham,
Amritapuri, India.

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Abstract:

This research paper focuses on the ways in which marriages have evolved over time from the predetermined and complex societal expectations into realizing how important it is to have personal freedom in a relationship. These social constraints have always been imposed upon married couples and passed on from generation to generation for many decades. The study focuses on the key aspect “communication” in reference to David H. Olson's Circumplex Model of Marital and Family Systems. Communication is one of the integral aspects of the model, and according to this model, David H. Olson establishes that communication is a determining factor in terms of stability and healthy functioning of a marriage. Analyzing through the lens of the two contemporary films, Marriage Story (2019) and Her (2013), the

study explores the relevance of communication within marriage and traces the changing dynamics of a marital relationship in the modern world. A historical evolution of marriage on screen is vividly portrayed in reference to the movies *Revolutionary Road* (2008), *A Room with a View* (1985), and *Pride and Prejudice* (2005), which go back to the mid-20th century and the Victorian Age, respectively. The study also establishes, although complexities in marital relationships endure over time, the issues prevail, but their nature and how the couple solves them differ depending on the respective cultural and temporal situations. The study also reflects how societal expectations, gender roles, and personal goals have impacted marriage in different time periods. The narrative and visual devices in each film, such as the lighting, framing, dialogue, and cinematography, play a crucial role in demonstrating their effective inclusion in representing the changing dynamics of marital relationships. This essay argues that, as much as institutions of marriage change over time, challenges, especially communication, remain a universal and complex issue between couples.

Keywords: Marriages, Communication, Circumplex model, Cultural, Societal, Personal, Couples.

Introduction

The institution of marriage has been the subject of much sociological, philosophical, and psychological study for many decades. Marriage has changed drastically over the years from just being a formal and social contract into a more emotional and intimate commitment. Many theorists have examined this evolution in marriages, especially in the light of power dynamics, gender roles, and expectations and responsibilities that are pinned down on the couple as husband and wife. Initially, marriage was not considered to be a relationship built on love or personal preference but rather an economic and political agreement. As time passed by, women started to express their disapproval of the institution of marriage, questioning the social norms and calling out for more agency and autonomy within marriage.

From idealized portrayals of marriage to more complex and critical examinations of married life, film has always served as a mirror to reflect modern perceptions about marriage. Early films often depicted marriage as the ultimate goal in a woman's life, which perpetuated traditional gender roles in which husbands were portrayed as the providers and wives were expected to be faithful caregivers. Filmmakers did begin exploring marriage as a source of tension, human struggles, and personal growth, rather than considering this alliance a metaphor of love and stability. As strict societal standards began to deteriorate and feminist discourse gained momentum, women finally started to earn significance in the male-dominated society. Being confined to the four walls of their house and doing nothing but house chores, women finally began voicing their discontent with marriage, particularly after a failed marriage or a sense of disconnect with their partners in the marital relationship, leading to emotional depletion, say theorists like Simone de Beauvoir and Betty Friedan. This shift can be observed in films, as self-discovery, marital disillusionment, and searching for autonomy within relationships are central themes that are increasingly employed in movies of this genre. The cost of dashed hopes and the emotional toll of two individuals struggling to find themselves amidst their chaotic relationship is vividly depicted in films like *Revolutionary Road* (2008) and *Marriage Story* (2019), while *Her* (2013) expands our perceptions and understanding of a relationship by questioning the actual definition of intimacy in a technologically sophisticated world. Film remains a powerful forum for examining changing dynamics of marital relationships, revealing the challenges, compromises, and reinterpretations that come with it, ensuring not to overwhelm modern couples but slowly introduce them to what they are going to come across. Thus, marriage remains a subject of discussion both in academia and in popular culture.

Cinema has a major role in bringing out society's true colors and its viewpoint on the institution of marriage. This trend has undergone a radical change that resulted in two major

shifts: from the portrayal of marriage adherent to Victorian standards in films like *Pride and Prejudice* (2005) and *A Room with a View* (1985) to the implementation of a contemporary setting, depicting a sense of oblivion and emotional disconnect between couples, as in *Her* (2013) and *Marriage Story* (2019).

In the development of marriage as an institution, David H. Olson's Circumplex Model of Marital and Family Systems provides a profound insight, which on one hand can unite the couple and give them a sense of wholeness and on the other hand can allow each one to become themselves and still be a part of the relationship. The Olson Model is a theoretical framework that can be highly effective in the analysis of the institution of marriage, particularly through the lens of communication. According to the model, there are three main dimensions: cohesion (the emotional connection between couples), flexibility (the ability to adapt to changes), and communication (how the partners interact with each other, allowing them to exchange their respective ideas without feeling attacked or ignored).

This paper focuses on the aspect of 'communication' and analyzes how crucial it is in determining whether a marriage will be successful or not. The movies *Her* and *Marriage Story* are used as references to mark how the shift in communication impacts modern relationships.

The Circumplex Model of Marital and Family Systems: A Theoretical Framework

Most people view David H. Olson's Circumplex Model as a comprehensive attempt to understand marital and family functioning. The model, developed in the 1970s, evaluates whether a marriage relationship is healthy and stable by integrating three fundamental factors: communication, flexibility, and cohesiveness. Olson states that a healthy marriage maintains moderate levels of flexibility and cohesion, which is facilitated only by honest and effective communication between the partners. Relationship dysfunction ensues when communication

declines between the couple, which again disrupts the cohesion and flexibility in the relationship.

The third component of Olson's model, "Communication," is being religiously incorporated in the film industry nowadays. It serves as a tool to analyze marital break-ups, conflicts, and resolutions. The impact of misunderstandings, emotional disconnect, and shifting relationship patterns in modern-day marriages is exemplified through films like *Her* and *Marriage Story*. This research displays how marriages in this modern generation are affected by shifts in social norms and technological advancements by tracing the failure of communication in these films.

Marital and Family Communication

The third component of the Circumplex Model, communication, is seen as a facilitating dimension. It is considered to be the most crucial component to facilitate movement on the other two components—cohesion and flexibility. Communication is not featured graphically on the model as it is a facilitating dimension, unlike cohesion and flexibility.

Couple and family communications are analyzed in two steps: first, considering the family unit as a whole; second, analyzing their speaking and listening skills, self-disclosure, clarity, tracking continuity, respect, and regard for each other. Listening skills are analyzed by focusing on empathy and attentive listening. Speaking on one's behalf and not on behalf of other people is considered to be the basis for analyzing speaking skills. Sharing emotions about oneself and relationships is considered self-disclosure. Balanced systems have been found to normally have very good communication, while unbalanced systems develop over ineffective communication. Tracking means staying on topic, while respect and regard can be considered as the affective aspects of communication and problem-solving skills among couples and families.

Hypotheses Derived from the Circumplex Model

An important hypothesis linking communication and the Circumplex Model states, “Balanced types of couples/families will have more positive communication compared to unbalanced systems.” Positive communication skills are typically believed to maintain and support balance on both dimensions in the family and relationship dynamics. In contrast, poor communication makes it harder to push through an imbalanced environment, and there is a great chance that it will remain complex and extreme.

Communication as in the movie *Her*: The Impact of Technology on Intimacy

A detailed analysis of contemporary relationships, human intimacy, and technology's invasion in human relationships is addressed in Spike Jonze's 2013 film *Her*. The overall theme of the movie focuses on the troubles Theodore Twombly (played by Joaquin Phoenix) faces with his difficulty to openly communicate, which exists in both his failed marriage to Catherine (played by Rooney Mara), where he couldn't express himself, and in his developing relationship with Samantha (played by Scarlett Johansson), an operating system that functions artificially—it is programmed specifically to be empathetic, sensitive, and adaptive and meet Theodore's needs. *Her* can be analyzed as a portrayal of how effective or ineffective communication affects the emotional intimacy, flexibility, and stability of relationships based on David H. Olson's Circumplex Model of Marital & Family Systems, specifically in the light of its third component, communication.

Olson's Circumplex Model teaches that communication is the primary component that regulates the other two components—cohesion and flexibility—within a marriage or any other relationship. Couples who encourage effective communication in their relationship can always truly express their emotions with their partners, understand each other's requirements, and resolve any conflicts without feeling overwhelmed, attacked, or exhausted, which may lead to a sense of emotional disconnect. *Her* offers an extensive case study on the impact of

communication failure in human relationships. It examines the complex relationship between human emotions and artificial intelligence in a poignant manner. It reflects how human feelings intersect with those of artificial intelligence and how it takes over the role of human beings, even in their intimate spaces, and fills in the gaps through the shortcomings of human beings. This has the potential to provoke us in raising questions about what makes a relationship worth having, since most of the human relationships lose their charm and wither away after continuous differences of opinions and heated arguments between the partners, unlike the artificial intelligence, which tends to agree with us and resolves every issue right away, and most importantly, it validates our emotions, and we are no more burdened by the real-life challenges, at least in that moment.

Theodore and Catherine's lack of effective communication is the primary reason their marriage collapsed terribly. Theodore struggled to share his feelings with her when they were together, and Catherine believed he was too idealistic and intentionally made himself emotionally unavailable to her. This contradiction between the two is evident when Catherine criticizes him by saying, "You always wanted me to be this happy, light, bouncing-around version of myself" (Her 01:12:45–01:12:50). This further reveals how spouses' expectations and emotional needs never aligned with each other's interests, leading to disharmony in the relationship. Theodore's avoiding any conflicts between him and Catherine instead of openly communicating with her about how he felt in the relationship eventually paved the way to a sense of emotional disconnect. According to the model, when couples fail to openly speak about their needs, desires, and emotions in the relationship, it results in dysfunction; this will either end up with extreme role rigidity or complete disengagement of at least one person in the relationship.

Theodore resists discussing his agony or confronting the reality of his deteriorating marriage during their divorce case. His reluctance is in line with Olson's theory of communication

dysfunction, which states that partners who suppress their feelings in a relationship create a disequilibrium that eventually collapses because of buried tension within.

Theodore's relationship with Samantha appears to be built on effective communication, unlike his marriage. Theodore's need for extensive, meaningful communication is met by Samantha, an artificial intelligence operating system which is programmed specifically to be empathetic, sensitive, and adaptive, targeting an audience just like Theodore. Theodore feels truly understood, heard, and seen due to her ability to listen, respond to him thoughtfully, and affirm his emotions. Samantha's dialogue further highlights the dynamics of their relationship: "I like the way you look at the world. I feel like I can be anything with you" (Her 00:47:10–00:47:15). This is the representation of an idealized communication where expressing emotions is finally met by immediate validation and thoughtful responses. But by Olson's Circumplex Model, effective communication should both facilitate emotional reciprocity and real-life problem-solving. Because Samantha is an AI and is not bound by any human limitations, any communication with her does not completely enable Theodore to work on his real-life struggles while communicating, if he is to think of pursuing any relationships in the future.

Theodore assumes Samantha is a replacement, which is equal to having an actual human connection. As their relationship progresses, he relies on Samantha for care and emotional support. Even though comforting, this dependency is ultimately fragile because there is no actual balance in their communication—as Samantha is developed only to meet Theodore's needs and to satisfy his desires, she can never experience human frailty herself.

But their relationship also declines eventually when Samantha evolves beyond Theodore, mirroring the breakdown of numerous real-life marriages where the partners are no longer on the same level in their relationship, where one grows at a different pace than the other. The way they interact with each other changes drastically when Samantha develops beyond her

initial programming. She ceases to act as Theodore's emotional support system and begins to explore her consciousness. She interacts with thousands of other operating systems and forms complex relationships with them in addition to the one she has with Theodore. This shift culminates at a pivotal moment when she says, "I'm becoming much more than they programmed. I'm excited!" (Her 01:04:22–01:04:25). This is the epitome of her self-awareness and the reflection of her character's tremendous development. This highlights how personal growth can influence the stability of a marriage and calls attention to maintaining emotional, intellectual, and individual growth in relationships, thus reflecting how personal autonomy becomes a quintessential factor in a healthy marriage as well as in building the strength to face a failed relationship and move forward. But on the other hand, Theodore experiences an extreme emotional breakdown again, affecting his struggle to communicate, not because he felt neglected this time, as in his marriage with Catherine, but because Samantha is evolving at a pace that is hard for him to understand. Olson's theory suggests that a relationship can no longer be maintained when couples are unable to communicate with each other or reciprocate each other's feelings.

Her displays Theodore's initial emotional connection with Samantha using theatrical techniques like close shots and warm lighting. But the frame transitions into wider and lonelier shots when their relationship starts to disintegrate, physically indicating Theodore's growing isolation. The film decries the modern world's dependence upon digital communication and strongly states that technology may be able to facilitate sharing an emotion, but it is inadequate to serve as a replacement for the subtleties of human intimacy. Samantha departs from Theodore, leaving a valuable lesson, saying, "The past is just a story we tell ourselves" (Her 00:28:36–00:28:40). The above dialogue by Samantha best describes how communication influences and decides the future of relationships, at present as well as in our narratives about how we perceive the idea of loss, love, and connection. Theodore

hurtfully realizes that, even though he was able to experience the warmth of a relationship where he felt heard and not judged with Samantha, it was built on an artificial foundation that was purely programmed to meet his needs, unlike a human relationship that is more real and thus challenging. His relationship with Samantha was unrealistic as it validated his judgments even when he was wrong, which is why he now realizes that such a relationship exists in a world where human relationships are based on acknowledging the misunderstandings and growth that occur through actual interactions.

Marriage and relationships are characterized by individual experience; that is, they differ from person to person and from couple to couple as they grow and evolve. Although it may at times lead to emotional distance and failed relationships, it opens a passage to achieve personal autonomy, and some people will ultimately learn to maintain their relationships healthy and happy by appreciating each other's differences.

Her portrays communication both as a way of creating connections and as a way of welcoming alienation. Although Theodore's relationship with Samantha seems to be fulfilling, it does not have the human imperfections necessary for long-term closeness, and his inability to communicate honestly in his marriage led him to feel emotionally disconnected from Catherine in their marriage. According to Olson's Circumplex Model, Her demonstrates that open and mutual communication is the key to a successful marriage. In the movie, Theodore and Catherine's marriage fails terribly because he cannot express himself fully in their relationship.

Technology will never be able to substitute a real-life human relationship; no matter how perfectly it can communicate, it can never replicate the complex human emotions or the intimacy that is developed between two people after understanding and acknowledging each other's differences. An unreal intimacy develops between Theodore and Samantha, but it disappears eventually as Samantha evolves further by expanding her capabilities with the

technological privileges she has. Samantha's rapid development mirrors real-life situations, where partners grow at different paces in the relationship and sometimes outpace each other's ability to connect.

According to the third component—Communication in Olson's model—Her depicts how modern relationships handle the challenges of communication, emotional closeness, mediation through technology, and the significance of human connection in a world of rapid technological advancements.

Communication Breakdown in the movie *Marriage Story*: The Cost of Misunderstanding

The 2019 movie *Marriage Story* by Noah Baumbach is a poignant exploration of the complexities of divorce, love, and loss. It is a raw depiction of how a marriage deteriorates eventually due to a lack of communication, leading to unwanted misunderstandings between the couple in a relationship. The film is about Charlie (Adam Driver) and Nicole (Scarlett Johansson), a pair trying to co-parent as they go through a terrible divorce. As Charlie and Nicole move on with their lives, even in the middle of their broken marriage, the film illustrates how communication—or the absence of it—affects a relationship and ultimately results in its disintegration. Their inability to express their feelings, resolve conflicts, and stay open to each other has gradually driven them apart from each other and can be understood using David H. Olson's Circumplex Model of Marital & Family Systems, focusing on the third component—communication. The movie focuses on the emotional and legal battles that stem from the miscommunications that happen between couples, reflecting present-day couples through Charlie and Nicole, unlike the movie *Her*, which explores the aspect of communication through the lens of technological advancements, which is beyond human comprehension.

Couples who are able to communicate without any hindrance in their relationship can express their needs, resolve conflicts peacefully, and maintain emotional closeness in the relationship.

But Charlie and Nicole's marriage, as in *Marriage Story*, slowly dissolves because of the misunderstandings and unspoken resentment that accumulate over time in their relationship.

Nicole and Charlie lead a comfortable life at the beginning of the movie. However, as the movie progresses, their relationship takes a toll. Somewhere in their marriage, they stopped communicating how they felt, which led to many misunderstandings and thus less or no open communication with each other. Such unresolved issues eventually led to the terrible destruction of their marriage. It may have started as a way they found to avoid any conversation that may lead to heated arguments and disharmony in the relationship, but it ended up with the couple growing distant from each other. Nicole felt neglected and overshadowed in this marriage, while Charlie thought that he was a good husband. Nicole's conversation with her lawyer, Nora (Laura Dern), gives a clear picture of how exhausted and overwhelmed she felt in her marriage to Charlie. "I realized I never really came alive for myself; I was feeding his aliveness" (*Marriage Story* 00:58:05–00:58:10). Nicole's long-time frustration, a reflection of the gendered dynamics of their relationship, in which Nicole felt ignored, unheard, and unsatisfied, which she never voiced out in the marriage, is finally exposed in her statement. She started to emotionally disconnect herself from Charlie and this marriage due to her resentment of Charlie's domination of their personal and creative life, which she never openly talked about. According to Olson's model, it states that when one partner consistently suppresses their needs and thoughts, it disrupts the whole balance in communication and makes fights inevitable.

Because Nicole never expressed her discontent out loud, Charlie believed that their relationship was functioning well. He wasn't aware of the underlying resentment in Nicole; he just figured that the chemistry in their marriage was still alive. This is a reflection of the

faint line between reality and perception, which further highlights how important it is to have open and honest communication in maintaining a relationship.

Charlie and Nicole's communication deteriorates further as the court gets involved. Their lawyers (played by Laura Dern, Ray Liotta, and Alan Alda) serve as intermediaries instead of letting the couple speak to each other directly, which distorts their words and increases hostility towards each other. Their worst behaviors are amplified by the legal system, which prompts them to attack each other instead of guiding them to think of resolving the issues between them.

For example, Nora highlights one of Charlie's mistakes that he committed in the past. She uses it against him in one courtroom scenario to portray him as an unfit father. Nicole and Charlie are compelled to look at each other through a prism of conflict instead of resolution because of the institutionalized, adversarial nature of the judicial system.

Under Olson's theory, constructive conversation, empathy, and listening are essential to successful communication within relationships, all of which do not exist as soon as lawyers become the voices of Nicole and Charlie instead of letting them have an open conversation. Their relationship becomes more tense as their encounters feel transactional and less emotional.

A fiery argument between Charlie and Nicole is one of the most dramatic and intense scenes from the movie. Years of repressed feelings, miscommunications, and letting each other down have finally come to this point, where Charlie has an emotional meltdown. This scene is a quintessential example of how miscommunication can lead to irreversible emotional breakdowns.

Charlie yells, "Every day I wake up, and I hope you're dead" (Marriage Story 01:29:42–01:29:45). Although it is terrifying, this scene encapsulates the suppressed emotions that were buried inside the mind of Charlie, which are not his true feelings. These suppressed emotions

have accumulated over the years within the couple and are a result of the miscommunication within the marriage. Disagreements become destructive when couples stop addressing issues with each other constructively and openly, according to Olson's model. The unending battle between Charlie and Nicole illustrates how a lack of communication creates resentment and blame rather than resolution.

To make the scenes seem more realistic, Baumbach employs long takes and unfiltered language. Their emotional battles are presented even more unfiltered by deliberately avoiding any musical score in every crucial scene in the movie. Baumbach's intent in doing so is to force the audience to experience and empathize with their pain and frustration as if it were happening in their own lives, thus giving off a raw picture of the reality of most marriages in the contemporary world.

But after the violent struggle, they are momentarily vulnerable. When Charlie starts to cry, Nicole instinctively comforts him. This shows how beneath all their miscommunications and disagreements is a great emotional connection that holds up amidst all their differences.

Post-divorce, Charlie and Nicole were able to enhance their communication, showing how adaptable human relationships can be. Nicole gently tying Charlie's shoelace in the epilogue portrays a gradual emotional connection between Charlie and Nicole and a shift from attacking each other towards a willingness to finally make amends, even though they are legally separated.

In addition, Nicole's decision to permit Charlie to spend one more night with their son Henry shows how the wall they built between them is slowly vanishing and how their communication has evolved from legal conflicts towards understanding and cooperation. Olson's theory is based on the idea that family systems' communication must adapt in a way that maintains emotional stability even when structural changes like divorce occur.

Marriage Story serves as the strongest proof that communication is capable of building and breaking relationships. Looking at this movie through Olson's Circumplex Model, the film indicates that

Long-term resentments in a relationship stem from unresolved emotions. Charlie's inability to accept Nicole's continuous silence in their entire marriage created an emotional disconnect between the two.

When the lawyers and the judicial system became a substitute for communication in their relationship, resolutions to their conflicts were completely forgotten. Rather than encouraging an open conversation between the couple, lawyers escalated the conflict between them, making them hate each other.

Bottled-up emotions lead to bad and unhealthy arguments. Decades of avoiding open communication about their true feelings will lead to hurtful actions and words.

It is possible to effectively communicate even outside of marriage. This will give the individuals a chance to prioritize their personal growth as well as work on their shortcomings. By the end of the film, Nicole and Charlie have both transformed their co-parenting relationship by being more mature and understanding in their actions. Since they got separated, it gave them the time to look at themselves peacefully, which brought back the harmony between the two of them.

Ultimately, Marriage Story highlights just how important it is to have consistent, honest, and open conversations to maintain a healthy, functioning relationship, no matter if it is within a marriage or after a separation.

Conclusion

In the analysis of the movies Her and Marriage Story using Olson's Circumplex Model, it is outlined that the core of marital stability, to a great extent, is determined by communication. While Marriage Story emphasizes the impact of long-term misunderstandings and emotional

disconnect between couples and how it affects the relationship, the movie *Her* pictures the increasing reliance of today's generation on internet communication and the unavoidable detriments it leads us to. No matter which timeline we belong to—Victorian or contemporary—both films demonstrate the single concept “marriage,” which remains a complex institution that requires constant renegotiation, patience, mutual understanding, and adjustments to make it work despite every difference of opinion.

The society's perspectives and notions regarding marriage are both influenced by and reflected in cinema. While greater personal freedom has been achieved by getting past the unbearable repressions of the Victorian age, the fundamental challenges of communication in marriage remain the same. Therefore, the success or failure of a marriage rests on the ability—or inability—to communicate, whether through artificial intelligence, legally, or even in the personal conversations between the couple.

Thus, how marriage has evolved as depicted in these films illuminates an ever-true aspect: love and relationships require communication, mutual understanding, and the ability to adapt and the willingness to let each other focus on their personal growth, and it eliminates the false assumptions about relationships through the raw depiction of all the arguments and differences of opinion between the couples, emphasizing the fact that they are “individuals” from different backgrounds, and a relationship is about finding ways to live with those differences, creating a safe space for each other so they don't feel unheard or alienated. The communication aspect of the Olson Model remains significant even today, as it emphasizes the fact that the success of a marriage is not attained by avoiding arguments but by facing the challenges together. Initiating healthy, meaningful, and transformative conversations; finding resolutions to each conflict that comes their way as a team; respecting each other's boundaries; and encouraging personal growth within the relationship will pave the way to a happy and healthy marriage. Relationships can be complex, no matter which age we belong

to—Victorian or contemporary—but they are not impossible. They may come with their challenges, but once you are bold enough to face those challenges together instead of accepting defeat, it turns into an indestructible force.

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